

**COMPLEX REHABILITATION METHODS IN PATIENTS WITH
OSTEOARTHRITIS DEPENDING ON THE PATHOGENETIC COURSE
OF THE DISEASE (Literature review)**

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Abstract. Literature data shows that osteoarthrosis is the most common pathology among joint diseases. This disease affects 10 to 16% of the world's population. As a person ages, the incidence of OA increases significantly. Thus, osteoarthrosis occurs in only 3-5% of patients under the age of 45, in 30% between the ages of 45 and 64, and in 60-70% of patients over the age of 65. Arthrosis of the knee joints is most common in 10% of the population over 55 years of age, and in 25% of cases there are clear signs of functional activity. Osteoarthritis of bones and joints is widespread, often has a chronic course, is accompanied by pain, limits the physical activity of patients, causes temporary or permanent disability, and has a heavy economic and psychological impact on patients.

Key words: *osteoarthrosis, knee joint, aseptic necrosis, periarticular anomaly, gonarthrosis, coxarthrosis, joint deformation.*

Today, there are many different treatments available to treat OA. However, despite the variety of treatment methods, they can be conditionally divided into conservative and surgical treatment methods. At the same time, some conservative methods are minimally invasive in part because they require puncturing the joint space. As part of conservative therapy, the following can be

mentioned: chondroprotectors (glucosamine and chondroitin preparations); physiotherapy; intra-articular injection of hormonal drugs; plasmolifting; nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs.

Onishchuk V.V. and b. In the authors' research, it was mentioned that the assessment of the possibility of therapeutic effect on the course of osteoarthritis. The complex of physiotherapeutic methods for the treatment of OA is very wide, and one of such methods is the high efficiency of peloidotherapy, which means that the clinical symptoms of OA can be improved and the quality of life of the patient can be seen to increase.

Interleukin (IL)-1b, -4, -6, -10, -17, -18, as well as tumor necrosis factor- α (FNO- α) play a key role in the development of OA.

Naturally, the effect of these cytokines on chondrocytes is accompanied by an increase in the synthesis of proteases, a tissue inhibitor of metalloproteases, a decrease in the synthesis of proteoglycans, an acceleration of catabolism processes in cartilage tissues, and an increase in the breakdown of cartilage matrix components.

Conservative treatment has a permanent positive effect only in the early stages of the disease. In the late stages, conservative treatment of gonarthrosis is ineffective and does not stop the development of the disease.

Analyzing the data presented in Russian and foreign sources, it can be said that cytokines are very important in the pathogenesis of OA. The analysis of the composition of cytokine networks, the dynamics of changes in their structure, the analysis of the relationship between the changes in the level of individual cytokines relative to each other, the development, improvement and introduction of drugs that can have a point effect on certain factors, and the representatives of the cytokine spectrum are the approach to the treatment of OA. fundamentally changes, because by effectively affecting the main link of pathogenesis, changing the course of the disease and thereby increasing the patient's chances of recovery,

as well as significantly reducing or completely abandoning the use of cyclooxygenase inhibitors, thereby preventing the occurrence of a number of complications typical of the use of nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs is to get In this quote, it is necessary to highlight the effectiveness of using a type of pharmacotherapy, i.e. a non-invasive method such as transcranial electrostimulation (TES-therapy) to affect the quantitative parameters of the cytokine profile.

In recent years, joint-preserving methods of treatment, along with total joint replacement operations, have been increasingly used in the orthopedic practice of treating patients with OA. Such traditional methods include conservative therapy with platelet-rich plasma (PRP-therapy), operative - corrective osteotomy, chondroplasty and other similar methods. The use of joint-preserving treatments can significantly improve the quality of life of patients and postpone the need for joint replacement for a long time, sometimes years. However, in the practice of orthopedics, they put forward the opinion that joint preservation methods cannot be used in elderly patients. The analysis carried out by the authors showed that there is no reliable information about the low efficiency of joint preservation methods in elderly patients, and all opinions about this are abstract. Joint-sparing methods have long been used in the treatment of patients with OA in the practice of the orthopedic department of a research hospital, and practical experience allows us to draw conclusions about their effectiveness in older patients. There are a large number of patients who cannot undergo arthroplasty or are very dangerous due to the presence of concomitant diseases. For these patients, the use of joint-sparing therapies is the only way to maintain mobility. During the last two years of the study, 1456 PRP therapy procedures were performed on 479 patients. Within one year, 76% of patients had a lasting therapeutic effect, such as a reduction in pain symptoms and an improvement in quality of life. At the same time, the complications typical of OA treatment with corticosteroids were almost

never observed. Among joint-preserving operations, this method is superior to arthroscopic and open options of chondroplasty due to its minimal damage and sufficient efficiency. In the early stages of work, chondroautoplasty was used, and later synthetic membrane materials were used more. Over the past two years, 56 open chondroplasty with synthetic materials have been performed on older patients. A positive result was noted in 72% of patients. This experience shows that joint-sparing approaches to the treatment of OA can be used as adjunctive methods in elderly patients when arthroplasty is impossible or dangerous for a number of reasons [8; p. 112].

Gilev Ya.Kh. et al. (2018) conducted an experience of using bone-ankle mosaic plasty in 25 patients with knee arthrosis. 16% of these patients were found to have defects in the articular cartilage. Long-term results were studied in 15 patients from 1 to 5 years. In 93.4% of them, a positive clinical result evaluated by the Leken index was recorded in the form of a decrease in the level of pain syndrome. The results of treatment in two patients were observed for 16 years. A stable remission of the disease was noted for 10 years. But later, the pain syndrome developed and worsened, which eventually became resistant to conservative therapy and required knee arthroplasty. Thus, the active use of bone-ankle mosaic plasty in patients with osteoarthritis of the knee with defects of the articular cartilage has a positive effect on improving the functional results of treatment and the prognosis of the disease, as well as the condition of delaying knee arthroplasty under the condition of careful selection of patients.

In the field of modern medicine, the problem of choosing treatment tactics for osteoarthritis of the knee joint is still a matter of debate. A large database of clinical studies and meta-analyses of the results of long-term use of surgical treatment methods such as treatment-diagnostic arthroscopy, corrective articular osteotomy of the femur and greater tibia, endoprosthetics of the medial and lateral areas of the knee joint, total knee endoprosthetics, and the rehabilitation function

of the limbs and shows high efficiency of pain reduction. Because of the high cost of total knee arthroplasty and the need for reoperation in younger patients, the demand for corrective osteotomy surgery is increasing. Such a study was conducted in the traumatology department of "Elizavetinskaya Hospital" in St. Petersburg in patients with arthrosis of the knee joint II-III level and the results were analyzed (Nazarov V. A. et al. 2019). The appearance of new symptoms along with X-ray signs of OA development was defined as an indication for a new surgical intervention, since the main goal of treatment is to improve the patient's quality of life. Usually, to determine the severity of knee arthrosis (2-3 stages of arthrosis), the authors recommend preliminary diagnostic arthroscopy. A varus deformity greater than 15 degrees requires a reduction osteotomy to the lesser fibula when valseizing external osteotomies. It is recommended to perform an oblique shortening osteotomy at the border of the middle and lower third, from the outside to the inside, from top to bottom, along the front surface, which helps to prevent pathological deformation of the lower third of the leg and leads to a decrease in the incidence of vascular and neurological disorders. The main factors that depend on the positive outcome of the treatment are good technical equipment, the availability of metal structures suitable for the selected treatment method, as well as having the necessary surgical skills of the attending physician. The choice of osteotomy method depends on the listed factors.

Ryabinin S.V. and b. (2019) the main goal of the scientists' research is to increase the clinical effectiveness of gonarthrosis treatment using an individual treatment scheme. 63 patients with stage II-III gonarthrosis were examined and treated. Patients included in the study were divided into 3 groups. Among them, patients in group I received standard treatment, patients in group II received AutoBoTP injection to standard treatment, and patients in group III received standard treatment, AutoBoTP injection and hyaluronic acid preparation. The condition of the patients before and after the treatment was assessed by means of

commonly accepted scales, questionnaires and determination of the electrolyte content of the synovial fluid. The best result was found in patients of group III. With a long period of remission, there was a decrease in pain intensity, an increase in range of motion due to a decrease in the $Sa^{2+}/RO43$ ratio, and a normalization of mineral metabolism in the synovial fluid. Thus, the use of this individual scheme recommended for the treatment of gonarthrosis made it possible to improve the results of treatment in patients and improve their quality of life [5; 66 b].

According to information in the literature, osteoarthritis is a disease with functional disorders and pain in the joints, and among such pathologies, gonarthrosis is the most common. Currently, effective treatment methods for such diseases are conservative, endoprosthesis and osteotomy. However, conservative treatment gives only a symptomatic effect, and endoprosthesis is recommended in moderate and severe degrees of osteoarthritis. Because relatively young patients require more preservation of the knee joint, they require minor surgical procedures and frequent revisions.

Based on the research conducted by these scientists, the method of osteotomy around the knee, based on the concept of "knee preservation", was chosen as an alternative surgical treatment. The cutting and realignment of the bones directs the mechanical line of the strong stresses on the feet. Thus, the osteotomy preserves the normal anatomical structure around the knee and ensures a good functional recovery of the knee joint. Osteotomy techniques around the knee include osteotomy against varus deformity and osteotomy against valgus deformity, which are aimed at redistributing severe stress in the knee joint compartment. Osteotomy around the knee, such as upper tibial osteotomy, proximal tibial osteotomy, distal femoral osteotomy, allows for mechanical axis correction by selecting the surgical site of the lower limbs. Many modified

methods based on traditional methods have been developed to meet the needs of patients. These modified osteotomies have their own advantages and indications.

Literature data show that physiotherapeutic treatment is an important method in the complex treatment of osteoarthritis. In addition to physical exercises, the structure of physical and rehabilitation medicine technologies for patients with OA includes various forms of acupuncture (conventional, laser puncture, electropuncture, burning), low-frequency electrotherapy, high-frequency therapy, laser therapy, and ultrasound (using nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory gels). . Also, the structure of technologies includes exercises using a pulsed magnetic field, braces and tapes (tape), massage, manual therapy, peloidotherapy, hydrotherapy, balneotherapy (Abuseva G. R., Kovlen D. V., Ponomarenko G. N. et al. 2013 .).

In case of pain syndrome, local electrophoresis with iodine and novocaine is performed in the joint area. In reactive synovitis, electrophoresis treatment with analgin, novocaine, salicylic has an analgesic, anti-inflammatory and hyposensitizing effect. In osteoarthritis, laser therapy is one of the main methods of treatment and has an anti-inflammatory and pain-relieving effect. The recovery time is reduced, swelling, pain is removed, microcirculation is restored.

In recent years, high tone therapy has been widely used in the West to treat OA. High tone therapy is characterized by periodic changes in the frequency of a wide range of alternating electric current from 4 kHz to 32 kHz. It has a vasodilating, neuromyostimulating, anti-tumor, anti-inflammatory, resorptive, trophic, spasmolytic, sympatholytic, gangliolytic, lipolytic effect .

In recent years, one of the widely used physiotherapeutic methods in the treatment of osteoarthritis is neuromuscular electrical stimulation (NMES). Due to the stimulation of nerve fibers, this method has a pain-relieving effect.

Zeng C. and. b. (2015) using low and high frequency transcutaneous electroneurostimulation (H-TENS and I-TENS), interference currents (IFC),

neuromuscular electrical stimulation (NMES), non-invasive neurostimulation (NIN), pulse electrostimulation (PES) methods, A randomized meta-analysis and a systematic review were conducted in patients with OA. As a result of this study, it was determined that interference currents have an analgesic effect. This contrasts with the minimal analgesic effect of h-TENS [140; p. 189].

Davudova A.K., Mamaykhanov S.M., Kudaev M.T. (2018) concluded that bromine-iodine baths (combined with other treatments) are the most effective treatment for elderly patients with knee OA. In addition to iodine-bromine baths (10 procedures, water temperature 36-37 °C, duration 10 minutes), which is the main medical complex, the following procedures are added: medical exercises 10-12 procedures daily, magnetotherapy and massage 8 procedures daily [27; p. 48].

Also Lepshokova A.B. (2017) in their research found a high efficiency (88.9%) of the complex use of therapeutic exercises in the pool, radon baths and magnetotherapy with dynamic variable magnetic field of low intensity, which was manifested by metabolic, anti-inflammatory and improvement of the quality of life of patients. One of the new methods of physiotherapy, which allows to obtain a pain-relieving effect without side effects, is high-intensity pulsed magnetic therapy (VIMT) with a magnetic induction value of 1.5-3 Tl. International studies show the high efficiency of SIS therapy (BTL-6000 Super Inductive System) in the treatment of diseases of the musculoskeletal system.

To date, most of what is known about the prevention and risk factors of osteoarthritis is related to the biology and pathophysiology of osteoarthritis, while several studies indicate that the risk factors for the disease are personal, financial, and social factors.

Thus, in the analysis of the literature, it is reflected that at the current stage of the treatment of osteoarthrosis in the stage of medical rehabilitation, this problem has been studied in different directions and specific aspects. However, it has been found that this is a difficult problem and there is no general consensus on

the treatment system. With this in mind, we believe that it is correct to study the effect of medical factors in relation to the level of joint pain and inflammation. In research and in the rehabilitation phase, treatment of osteoarthritis patients with physical and natural factors is approached to be based on the results obtained when the treatment is carried out in combination with other means.

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